

On the limitations of the Flat-Ground Postulate in downslope bushfire propagation

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Abstract

This article examines mathematical models for the rate of spread of bushfires across inclined terrains. We analyze a specific postulate that has been adopted in the literature asserting that the rate of spread across an undulating landscape is well approximated by that of fire spreading across flat ground.

We prove that the downslope equations proposed in the bushfire literature are equivalent to this postulate holding for symmetric hills. In contrast, we further prove that, if the postulate holds for all hills, then the rate-of-spread function must take a specific form not seen in established empirical models.

Our findings demonstrate that the assumption such a postulate holds in full generality may be too restrictive for applications, and calls for further empirical and theoretical investigation to determine when it can be assumed to hold.

1 Introduction

1.1 Objective of this article

A topical problem in bushfire modeling is to estimate the rate at which the front of a given fire spreads. One of many factors known to impact this rate is the angle of the terrain's inclination.

In this article, we investigate mathematical models for the rate of bushfire spread across inclined terrains, focusing on the relationship between terrain slope and fire front velocity. While existing empirical models, such as the widely used exponential model, are primarily validated for upslope spread, significant ambiguity remains regarding downslope propagation. We specifically analyze a prevalent axiomatic approach, postulating that the time required for a fire to cross an undulating landscape is equivalent to the time taken to cross over flat ground, which has been used to derive downslope correction factors.

We analyze the implications of this postulate when applied to different terrain profiles. We prove that, when the postulate is applied to symmetric terrains, it is equivalent to the

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downslope equations proposed in the classical bushfire literature. We prove also that, should the postulate hold over general terrain, we are forced to adopt a model of a very specific form, which exhibits a structural incompatibility with established upslope models.

1.2 Background and literature review

In the literature on this topic, it is convention to denote the rate of spread by R , and the angle of the terrain’s inclination by θ . For mathematical convenience, in this paper we measure θ in radians, with $\theta = 0$ corresponding to horizontal terrain and $\theta = \pi/2$ to a vertical wall.

To isolate the effect of θ , it is common to assume all other variables are held constant. In what follows, we too make this assumption, and adopt the functional notation $R = R(\theta)$.

To simplify notation, we adopt the convention that R is normalized such that $R(0) = 1$ (in this sense, R represents here a relative rate of spread, or “spread-rate multiplier”).

As pointed out by [Sul+14], there are two natural, non-equivalent interpretations of R , depending on the direction in which spread is measured. One can either measure in the direction tangent to the terrain (along the ground), or perpendicular to the force of gravity (from a “birds eye view”). These two measurements, which we denote T and F respectively, are related via

$$F(\theta) = \cos(\theta)T(\theta). \tag{1}$$

For small values of θ , the difference is $O(\theta^2)$ and thus negligible. However, the distinction may matter for larger values (e.g., $\cos(0.698) \simeq 0.766$, which would affect the result by about 23%). In this paper, we will focus on the function F , with the understanding one can easily convert between T and F via equation (1).

The distinction between the two measurements in (1) is not always acknowledged in the literature, leading to models being stated in terms of the ambiguous parameter R , potentially meaning either T or F . This ambiguity is present in one of the most influential models for the relationship between R and θ , due to [NGB80], which takes the form

$$R(\theta) = e^{C\theta}, \tag{2}$$

where $C \approx 3.953$. The value of C is chosen such that R approximately doubles with every 10 degrees of inclination.¹ Equation (2) here above is adapted from empirical fire danger meters introduced by [McA67]. They are purportedly valid for $\theta \in [-0.698, 0.698]$, that is approximately ± 40 degrees,² though this domain of validity has been questioned.³

For positive values of θ , equation (2) enjoys broad application. However, its use for negative θ typically leads to an underestimate. For this reason, [Cru+15] instead recommend the use of the function

$$F(\theta) = \frac{1}{2 - e^{C\theta}}, \tag{3}$$

for $\theta < 0$, the constant C being the same as in (2).

¹See equation (2) in [Sul+14].

²See the comment after equation (2) in [Sul+14].

³For example, [Cru+15] give a domain of 0 to 20 degrees (see the comment after equation (2.1)), and [Che81] suggest it should not be used outside the range ± 30 degrees.

This model is due to [Sul+14], who name it *kataburn* (*kata* meaning “down” in Greek). The model has been extensively utilized, analyzed, recommended, and cited in wildfire research as a benchmark downslope correction. Examples are:

- The year after [Sul+14] was published, one of the paper’s authors wrote an article in the CSIRO’s *PyroPage* on the advantages of the kataburn model [Sul15]. It is noted in this article that “*the error is much reduced compared to*” equation (2), and the kataburn model is called “*a much more practical version for operational implementation than the complete solution which requires information about the upslope component of the terrain*”. The article also captions a graph⁴ of the kataburn model as “*Graph of recommended slope correction factor values for Australian fire spread models*”.
- The model was presented in [Cru+15] in the section regarding the “*slope steepness effect on bushfire spread rate*”, mentioning that “*the kataburn model utilises the upslope function to determine the downslope correction factor*”; the explicit kataburn formula is reproduced in [Cru+15, equation (2.2)].
- The issues raised by [Sul+14] in using equation (2) were discussed in [Inn22, page 45], though they do not discuss the kataburn model directly.
- The model was presented at the beginning of the introduction in [Jia+22] as one of the resources that “*use experimental data to construct empirical functions of environmental parameters and fire spread rates*”.
- The official documentation for Spark (a toolkit for wildfire simulation and analysis developed by the CSIRO) contains code implementing the kataburn model [CSI26].

Critical remarks have also appeared in the literature. For instance:

- An evaluative discussion of the kataburn model was put forth in [EGS23], who note the model is “*based on the general observation that over large distances (i.e. kilometres), fires burning in undulating terrain exhibit similar overall rates of spread to fires burning over flat ground*”, and go on to write “*this approach overlooks the finer-scale dynamics that can influence fire behaviour at sub-kilometre scales*”.
- The model was compared against experimental data in [Rio18] and described as a “*geometrically derived [...] correlation called kataburn that, coupled with the mentioned factors, improves the performance of downwards propagation. Despite the outperformance when compared to experimental data, its application is reduced to simple constant slope hills (i.e. triangles). Moreover, when hills are not symmetrical (i.e. same upslope than downslope) the results are considerable worse*”.⁵

From the point of view of bushfire managing, the importance of the models constructed by [Sul+14] is due not to their theoretical soundness, but their empirical performance. This point is made by [Sul+14] themselves, who say that “*While the postulates upon which this*

⁴See Figure 2 of [Sul15].

⁵With regard of this criticism, our article gives a mathematical explanation of this experimental evidence.

work is based may be largely anecdotal and unquantified, the performance of the kataburn models against the data suggests that there is some basis to them.”

However, [Sul+14] derive the kataburn model not on empirical grounds, but theoretical ones: the crux of their argument involves a deduction from two postulates. Of these postulates, the authors write “...it may be possible to calculate a downslope spread correction factor that is broadly applicable to determining rate of spread across the landscape given two postulates:

1. *The relative rates of spread provided by existing upslope spread correction factors are appropriate in the context of fire behaviour at the broader landscape scale as well as the laboratory.*
2. *The rate of spread of a large fire burning across an undulating landscape is well approximated by that of fire spreading across a corresponding expanse of flat ground.”*

This axiomatic approach is conceptually appealing in that it decomposes the downhill spread problem into two distinct components. On the one hand, Postulate 1 assumes that classical models are approximately valid for positive slopes when used within their intended range. On the other hand, Postulate 2, which we informally name the *Flat-Ground Postulate* (FGP, for short), establishes a general reconstruction principle for fire spread over arbitrary terrains, combining both uphill and downhill contributions from knowledge of the uphill spread alone.

It is argued in [Sul+14] that the FGP, along with the values of $F(\theta)$ for $\theta \geq 0$, determine completely the values for $\theta < 0$, via the formula

$$F(-\theta) = \frac{1}{2 - \frac{1}{F(\theta)}}. \quad (4)$$

Note that (3) is the result of applying formula (4) to (2), assuming⁶ that $R = F$.

In [Sul+14], equation (4) here is obtained by considering a symmetric, triangular hill with base length $2D$, as in Figure 1. The time taken for a fire to cross this hill is

$$\frac{D}{F(\theta)} + \frac{D}{F(-\theta)}.$$

Now, if the ground were flat, then the time would instead be $2D/F(0) = 2D$. Via the FGP, they argue, these quantities must be equal, so

$$2D = \frac{D}{F(\theta)} + \frac{D}{F(-\theta)}. \quad (5)$$

Rearranging yields (4).

We emphasize that this argument yields (4) by applying the FGP to a single terrain configuration, namely the symmetric triangular hill depicted in Figure 1. Applying this argument

⁶In recommending the use of (3), [Cru+15] implicitly assume $R = F$. However, [Sul+14] do not, providing different formulas for the $R = F$ and $R = T$ interpretations, which they call kataburn-A and kataburn-B respectively (see equations (11) and (12) in [Sul+14]). In fact, [Sul+14] claim kataburn-B yields a better fit for experimental data.

Figure 1: A symmetric triangular hill

to other configurations, however, yields differing equations. For example, an asymmetric triangular hill, such as in Figure 2, yields the equation

$$F(-\alpha) = \frac{\kappa}{(1 + \kappa) - \frac{1}{F(\theta)}}, \quad (6)$$

where $\kappa := \tan(\theta)/\tan(\alpha)$. This should be seen as problematic, since (6) does not match, in general, with (4). As a matter of fact, formula (6) was also obtained by [Sul+14],⁷ but immediately discarded there. They argue that, due to its simultaneous dependence on θ and α , equation (6) “cannot be used for practical fire spread simulations”.

Figure 2: An asymmetric triangular hill, where $\kappa = \tan(\theta)/\tan(\alpha)$.

Nonetheless, the discrepancy between (4) and (6) calls for additional investigation. It suggests that different conclusions can be drawn about the rate of propagation, depending on which terrains the FGP is assumed to be valid over. This further research is important for practical applications, as understanding how the implications of the FGP depend on its assumed domain allows for it to be tested experimentally in a systematic and thorough manner.⁸

1.3 Main results

To investigate the issues mentioned above, we consider a fire spreading across a general hilly terrain, between two points that lie at the same height (placed, for simplicity, at $-D$ and D , for some fixed $D > 0$). We represent such terrain as the graph of a continuous, piecewise C^2

⁷See equation (18) in [Sul+14].

⁸We plan to run specific experiments on this topic, to detect the effect of symmetric and asymmetric slopes on bushfire propagation, and the possible memory effects produced by the different order at which a fire front travels through different topographies. The results collected in these experiments will be the subject of a forthcoming paper.

function $\gamma : [-D, D] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, with well-defined and bounded one-sided derivatives at all points of $[-D, D]$, and such that $\gamma(-D) = 0 = \gamma(D)$. We denote by \mathcal{T} the set of all such γ (see Figure 3). We also make the assumption that F is C^2 and strictly positive.

Figure 3: Arbitrary terrain $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$

Given $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$, we denote by $\tau(\gamma)$ the time taken⁹ for a fire to spread from $x = -D$ to $x = D$ along γ . Note that, since the function $\gamma = 0$ represents flat terrain, we have $\tau(0) = 2D$. In this setting, we say the FGP holds for γ if the time taken for the fire to spread across γ equals the time taken to spread along flat ground. That is, if $\tau(\gamma) = 2D$.

Our first result deals with the case in which the FGP holds for all $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$. This case is very restrictive, and in fact forces F to be a function of a very specific form:

Theorem 1. *The FGP holds for all $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$ if and only if*

$$F(\theta) = \frac{1}{1 + c \tan(\theta)}, \quad (7)$$

for some constant c .

To the best of our knowledge, functions of the form (7) do not match any model established in the literature, even for positive slopes. In this sense, Theorem 1 suggests that applying the FGP to general terrains is structurally incompatible with classical bushfire models.

We now consider cases in which the FGP is only assumed to hold on a subset of \mathcal{T} . In view of the derivation presented in [Sul+14], two natural choices are:

- The set $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}$ of hills with the same initial and final slope, corresponding to functions γ which satisfy $\gamma'(-D) = -\gamma'(D)$.
- The set \mathcal{S} of symmetric hills, corresponding to even functions γ (see Figure 4).

Notice that $\mathcal{S} \subset \tilde{\mathcal{T}} \subset \mathcal{T}$.

Figure 4: Arbitrary symmetric terrain $\gamma \in \mathcal{S}$. Notice that $\gamma'(-x) = -\gamma'(x)$.

It turns out that restricting the FGP to the class $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}$ does not alter the previous result:

⁹We provide an explicit formula for $\tau(\gamma)$ in the following section (see equation (9)).

Theorem 2. *The FGP holds for all $\gamma \in \widetilde{\mathcal{T}}$ if and only if equation (7) holds.*

The situation differs for the class of symmetric terrains. The assumption the FGP holds on \mathcal{S} is precisely equivalent to equation (4):

Theorem 3. *The FGP holds for all $\gamma \in \mathcal{S}$ if and only if*

$$F(-\theta) = \frac{1}{2 - \frac{1}{F(\theta)}},$$

in agreement with (4).

The combination of these results is interesting because:

- On the one hand Theorem 3 proves that the equation proposed by [Sul+14] is equivalent to the FGP holding for all symmetric landscapes.
- On the other hand, Theorem 1 suggests that the assumption the FGP holds on general terrains is incompatible with existing bushfire literature (and, by Theorem 2, that this incompatibility persists even if the FGP is restricted to hills with the same initial and final slope).

We now dive into the analytical details needed to prove these results.

2 Proofs of main results

2.1 Preliminaries

Let $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$. We denote by Σ_γ the finite (possibly empty) set of points at which γ fails to be C^2 (recall that all members of \mathcal{T} are piecewise C^2).

In the following calculations, it will be convenient to express F as a function of the terrain's slope $s = \tan(\theta)$, rather than the angle of inclination. This amounts to the substitution

$$M(s) := F(\arctan s). \tag{8}$$

Note that $M(0) = F(0) = 1$, and that our assumptions F is C^2 and strictly positive transfer to M as well.

Let $x(t)$ denote the front of a fire spreading across γ , starting at $x(0) = -D$. If $x(t) \notin \Sigma_\gamma$, then $\tan(\theta(t)) = \gamma'(x(t))$, therefore

$$x'(t) = F(\theta(t)) = M(\gamma'(x(t))).$$

Thus, since γ' is bounded, we have that $x'(t)$ is bounded away from zero and accordingly there is a unique time $\tau(\gamma)$ at which $x(t) = D$ (as implicitly assumed on page 6). Now, $\tau(\gamma)$ may be computed as

$$\tau(\gamma) = \int_0^{\tau(\gamma)} 1 dt = \int_0^{\tau(\gamma)} \frac{x'(t)}{M(\gamma'(x(t)))} dt = \int_{-D}^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx. \tag{9}$$

Therefore, the FGP holds for γ if and only if

$$\int_{-D}^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx = 2D. \quad (10)$$

Equation (9) is useful, as it expresses $\tau(\gamma)$ in terms of γ and M alone, and not the function $x(t)$. This allows for calculations to be performed for arbitrary $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$, extending those performed by [Sul+14] for triangular hills. In particular, if $\gamma(x) = \tan(\theta)(D - |x|)$ (which corresponds to the symmetric triangular hill in Figure 1), then by (10) the FGP holds for γ if and only if

$$\begin{aligned} 2D &= \int_{-D}^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx = \int_{-D}^0 \frac{1}{M(\tan(\theta))} dx + \int_0^D \frac{1}{M(-\tan(\theta))} dx \\ &= \frac{D}{M(\tan(\theta))} + \frac{D}{M(-\tan(\theta))} \\ &= \frac{D}{F(\theta)} + \frac{D}{F(-\theta)}, \end{aligned}$$

which is precisely (5).

Given an open interval $I \subseteq \mathbb{R}$ we denote by $\mathcal{T}_c^\infty(I)$ the set of functions $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}$ which are smooth and have compact support contained in I . Given a subset $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$, we define $\mathcal{A}_c^\infty(I) = \mathcal{A} \cap \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(I)$. When writing the interval explicitly as $I = (a, b)$, we abuse notation by writing $\mathcal{T}_c^\infty(a, b)$, rather than $\mathcal{T}_c^\infty((a, b))$.

Let $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{T}$ be any vector subspace of \mathcal{T} . If the FGP holds on \mathcal{A} , then the functional $\tau : \mathcal{T} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by $\gamma \mapsto \tau(\gamma)$ is constant on \mathcal{A} , by equation (9) and (10). In particular, this requires that

$$\left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \tau(\gamma + \varepsilon\eta) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = 0,$$

for all $\gamma, \eta \in \mathcal{A}_c^\infty(-D, D)$.

Now, for all $\gamma, \eta \in \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(-D, D)$, we compute

$$\left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \tau(\gamma + \varepsilon\eta) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = - \int_{-D}^D \frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \eta'(x) dx.$$

Hence, integrating by parts,

$$\left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \tau(\gamma + \varepsilon\eta) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = \int_{-D}^D \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \right] \eta(x) dx.$$

In this spirit, the assumption that τ is constant on \mathcal{A} entails that, for all $\gamma, \eta \in \mathcal{A}_c^\infty(-D, D)$,

$$\int_{-D}^D \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \right] \eta(x) dx = 0. \quad (11)$$

2.2 Proof of Theorems 1 and 2

Since $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} \subset \mathcal{T}$, we can prove Theorems 1 and 2 simultaneously by showing that

$$\text{if the FGP holds for all } \gamma \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}}, \text{ then equation (7) holds} \quad (12)$$

and

$$\text{if equation (7) holds, then the FGP holds for all } \gamma \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (13)$$

We first prove (12). Suppose that τ is constant on $\tilde{\mathcal{T}}$. Let $\varepsilon \in (0, D)$ and $I_\varepsilon := (-D + \varepsilon, D - \varepsilon)$. Since $\tilde{\mathcal{T}} \supseteq \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(I_\varepsilon)$, one deduces from (11) that

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \right] = 0,$$

for all $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(I_\varepsilon)$ and $x \in I_\varepsilon$. Accordingly, for all $x \in I_\varepsilon$,

$$\frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} = B_\gamma, \quad (14)$$

for some constant B_γ , possibly depending on γ . It follows that (14) holds true for all $x \in [-D, D]$, since we can take ε as small as we wish.

Choose $\gamma_1 \in \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(-D, D)$ such that $\gamma_1'(D/2) = 1$, and denote $B = B_{\gamma_1}$. Since $\gamma_1'(D) = 0$ (as it is compactly supported in $(-D, D)$), it follows from (14) that

$$B = \frac{M'(\gamma_1'(D))}{M^2(\gamma_1'(D))} = \frac{M'(0)}{M^2(0)}.$$

For all $s \in \mathbb{R}$, let $\gamma_s := s\gamma_1 \in \tilde{\mathcal{T}}$. Since $\gamma_s'(D) = 0$, and $\gamma_s'(D/2) = s$, we similarly have

$$B = \frac{M'(0)}{M^2(0)} = \frac{M'(s)}{M^2(s)},$$

for all $s \in \mathbb{R}$. Integrating this last equation in s yields

$$\frac{1}{M(s)} = A - Bs,$$

for some constant A , and then, by (8),

$$\frac{1}{F(\theta)} = \frac{1}{M(\tan \theta)} = A - B \tan \theta.$$

Recalling our convention $F(0) = 1$, it follows $A = 1$. This proves (12), as desired.

Now, to prove (13), it suffices to recall (9) and observe that, if $M(s) = 1/(1 + cs)$, then

$$\tau(\gamma) = \int_{-D}^D (1 + c\gamma'(x)) dx = 2D + c(\gamma(D) - \gamma(-D)) = 2D,$$

showing the validity of the FGP. □

2.3 Proof of Theorem 3

To start with, we assume that the FGP holds for all $\gamma \in \mathcal{S}$ (hence τ is constant on \mathcal{S}), and we show (4) holds. For all $\gamma \in \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(-D, D)$, define

$$H_\gamma(x) := \frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \quad \text{and} \quad G_\gamma(x) := H'_\gamma(x).$$

Notice that, if $\gamma \in \mathcal{S}_c^\infty(-D, D)$, we have

$$\gamma'(-x) = -\gamma'(x). \tag{15}$$

(See Figure 4.) Accordingly

$$H_\gamma(-x) = \frac{M'(-\gamma'(x))}{M^2(-\gamma'(x))} = H_{-\gamma}(x).$$

Therefore, we find that

$$G_\gamma(-x) = H'_\gamma(-x) = -\frac{d}{dx}(H_\gamma(-x)) = -\frac{d}{dx}(H_{-\gamma}(x)) = -H'_{-\gamma}(x) = -G_{-\gamma}(x),$$

and we can rewrite (11) in this case as

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_{-D}^D \frac{d}{dx} \left[\frac{M'(\gamma'(x))}{M^2(\gamma'(x))} \right] \eta(x) dx \\ &= \int_{-D}^D G_\gamma(x) \eta(x) dx \\ &= \int_0^D G_\gamma(x) \eta(x) dx + \int_0^D G_\gamma(-x) \eta(-x) dx \\ &= \int_0^D (G_\gamma(x) - G_{-\gamma}(x)) \eta(x) dx, \end{aligned}$$

for all $\gamma, \eta \in \mathcal{S}_c^\infty(-D, D)$. Since this last integral is only over $[0, D]$, it follows that this last equation holds for arbitrary $\eta \in \mathcal{T}_c^\infty(0, D)$. As a consequence,

$$0 = G_\gamma(x) - G_{-\gamma}(x) = H'_\gamma(x) - H'_{-\gamma}(x),$$

for all $x \in [0, D]$. This gives that

$$H_\gamma(x) - H_{-\gamma}(x) = C_\gamma$$

for all $x \in [0, D]$ and some constant C_γ , potentially depending on γ .

Now, by (15), we must have $\gamma'(0) = 0$, so substituting $x = 0$ into the previous equation yields

$$C_\gamma = H_\gamma(0) - H_{-\gamma}(0) = \frac{M'(0)}{M^2(0)} - \frac{M'(0)}{M^2(0)} = 0.$$

On this account, given $s \in \mathbb{R}$, and picking $\gamma \in \mathcal{S}_c^\infty(-D, D)$ such that $\gamma'(D/2) = s$, we deduce that

$$\frac{M'(s)}{M^2(s)} - \frac{M'(-s)}{M^2(-s)} = 0.$$

Integrating with respect to s , it follows

$$\frac{1}{M(s)} + \frac{1}{M(-s)} = D,$$

for some constant D . Since $M(0) = F(0) = 1$, substituting $s = 0$ into this equation yields $D = 2$. Accordingly, by (8),

$$\frac{1}{F(\theta)} + \frac{1}{F(-\theta)} = 2,$$

for all $\theta \in \mathbb{R}$. This proves that (4) holds true, as claimed.

To prove the reverse implication, it suffices to notice that, if M satisfies

$$\frac{1}{M(s)} + \frac{1}{M(-s)} = 2,$$

then, by (9),

$$\begin{aligned} \tau(\gamma) &= \int_{-D}^0 \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx + \int_0^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx \\ &= \int_0^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(-y))} dy + \int_0^D \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} dx \\ &= \int_0^D \left(\frac{1}{M(-\gamma'(x))} + \frac{1}{M(\gamma'(x))} \right) dx \\ &= 2D, \end{aligned}$$

showing that the FGP holds true in this case. □

3 Conclusions

Since its introduction, the kataburn model in equation (3) has become a benchmark in wild-fire research and the management of bushfire events. Instead of theoretical considerations, proponents of the model point to its empirical performance, noting it is superior to that of prior models. Despite this, the kataburn model is actually derived on theoretical grounds, namely the Flat-Ground Postulate (FGP). In this paper, we have examined the implications of assuming the FGP holds for various classes of terrain.

If the FGP is assumed to hold over all terrains, then the model is forced to take the specific form seen in equation (7). This is of interest since, to the best of our knowledge, such models do not match those established in the literature, even for positive slopes. This suggests that the assumption the FGP holds over general terrains is not compatible with existing bushfire literature.

In contrast, the weaker assumption that the FGP holds over symmetric landscapes is precisely equivalent to the downslope correction formula (4) proposed by [Sul+14]. The fact equation (4) follows from this assumption is not new, as [Sul+14] derive it from applying the FGP to symmetric triangular hills as in Figure 1. What is new here is the reverse implication: if the FGP holds for triangular symmetric hills, then it actually holds for *all* symmetric hills. This has practical implications for designing experiments to test the validity of equation (4), as one can test the FGP on any symmetric hill, not necessarily triangular. Our findings, however, further indicate that the validity of the FGP on general terrains poses conceptual challenges for the overall bushfire analysis paradigm.

An important aspect of this discussion is an assumption made at the outset of this paper, as well as in [Sul+14]. Namely, that all other variables which may impact R are held constant. Of course, this assumption is made so that the effect of θ can be analyzed in isolation. But even ignoring variance in factors such as fuel type and weather, this still comes with the rather strong assumption that the rate of spread is *memoryless*, in the sense that it does not depend on the terrain seen previously.

To address the discrepancies between theoretical reconstructions and real-world fire behavior, a forthcoming paper will detail specific laboratory experiments designed to test the effects of asymmetric slopes on bushfire propagation and to investigate potential memory effects as a fire front traverses different topographies.

The findings of this paper provide a conceptual framework for understanding the applicability and limitations of the FGP, contributing to our understanding of bushfire propagation models and the practical implications of deductive methodologies in fire event management. They also inform the design of experimental tests aimed at validating and refining such models, while opening avenues for the development of new modeling approaches.

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